

Studies on 4-hydroxy-1-thiacoumarins: Part IV*. Synthesis of 3-substituted-aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-1-thiacoumarins

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A series of 3-substituted-aminomethyl-4-hydroxy 1-thiacoumarins have been synthesised by the application of the Mannich reaction. The quantitative formation of 3,3'-methylene-bis-(4-hydroxy-1-thiacoumarin) through acid treatment of the Mannich base obtained from 4-hydroxy-1-thiacoumarin and piperidine is recorded and discussed.

In an earlier communication¹ has been recorded the results of the reaction between 4-hydroxy-1-thiacoumarin and formaldehyde. This involves an aldol type of condensation between two molecules of 4-hydroxy-1-thiacoumarin (in the tautomeric 2,4-diketothiacroman form) and one molecule of formaldehyde and illustrates a case of *nucleophilic* substitution at the active methylene carbon atom in the 3-position. A logical extension of such a reaction will be a study of the Mannich reaction between such active methylene compounds like 4-hydroxy-1-thiacoumarin, formaldehyde and various primary and secondary amines. Such a study has now been carried out and the results recorded. The products of this reaction have been the 3-aminomethyl derivatives (II).

Since the reaction between 4-hydroxy-1-thiacoumarin (I) and formaldehyde to give the 3,3'-methylene-bis compounds (III) is a very rapid one, the order in which the reactants are added to make the Mannich reaction possible is important.

where R is hydrogen or alkyl and R' is alkyl or aralkyl, or where NRR' makes up a heterocyclic ring.

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1. P. S. Jamkhandi and S. Rajagopal, Studies on 4-hydroxy-1-thiacoumarins (III), *Monatsh*, 1966, **97**, 1732.

(III)

This is achieved by adding a solution of 4-hydroxy-1-thiacoumarin (1.00 mole) in absolute ethanol to a solution of the amine (1.25 mole) and formalin (1.00 mole) in absolute ethanol at room temperature. Further it has been found that the ease with which the Mannich reaction proceeds with the various amines differ greatly depending on the nature of the amine employed. The reaction proceeds very fast in the case of the primary amines while it is relatively slow when secondary amines are employed. Thus while in the former case the reaction could proceed at room temperature, in the latter case the reactants had to be mixed at the boiling point and subsequently allowed to stand for a number of hours.

It is well known that many of the products obtained in the Mannich reaction, especially those derived from secondary amines undergo decomposition into the amine and unsaturated compound². The intermediate formation of such compounds has also been postulated by Robertson and Link³ to explain the quantitative formation of 3,3'-methylene-bis-(4-hydroxycoumarin), when the Mannich reaction product (IV) of 4-hydroxycoumarin with piperidine is heated in an aqueous acid solution at 100°. It was suggested by these authors that the Mannich base decomposes to an unsaturated compound (3-methyldene-2,4-diketochroman) (V) which in turn undergoes reverse aldol reaction to give 4-hydroxycoumarin (I). Subsequently interaction of one molecule of the former with one molecule of the latter compound gives dicoumarol (III). The course of the reaction may probably be represented as shown below:

2. Blicke in Adam's, "Organic Reactions", Vol. I. John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, N. Y., 1942, p. 318.

3. D. N. Robertson and K. P. Link, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 1883.

It has now been found that the Mannich reaction product obtained employing 4-hydroxy-1-thiacyoumarin (I), formaldehyde and piperidine behaves in a similar manner, when heated in an aqueous acid solution.

These 3-substituted-aminomethyl 4-hydroxy-1-thiacyoumarins were tested for their anticoagulant activity adopting the method of Quick *et al*⁴ which involves the determination under standard conditions of the time required for the clotting of recalcified plasma in the presence of an excess of added thromboplastin. None of the compounds recorded in this paper was found active.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of 3-substituted-aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-1-thiacyoumarins: A solution of the appropriate amine (0.003 mole) in absolute ethanol (3 ml.) was treated with formaldehyde (40%) (0.0025 mole). To this solution was added 4-hydroxy-1-thiacyoumarin (0.0025 mole) in absolute ethanol (5 ml.).

In the case of primary amines the reactants were mixed at room temperature when the products usually began to separate within short time. Crystallisation was completed by allowing the reaction mixture to stand in the refrigerator at 5° for about 2 hr. The products were filtered and washed with ether. The yields and physical constants are recorded in table I.

With the secondary amines, the reactants were mixed at the boiling point of the ethanolic solution, allowed to cool at room temperature and stored at 5° overnight. The separated products were filtered and washed with dry ether. By diluting the mother liquors with ether, additional quantities of the products could be obtained. The yields and physical constants are recorded in the table.

TABLE I

3-Substituted-aminomethyl-4-hydroxy-1-thiacyoumarins (II)

R	R'	Yield %	M.P.° C	Molecular formula (221)	Analysis	
					Found	Calc.
H	CH ₃	55	301-303 (Bright yellow long needles)	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS (221)	C 60.08 H 4.86	59.71 4.97

Table I Contd.

R	R ¹	Yield %	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis	
					Found	Calc.
H	C ₂ H ₅	59	298-300 (Colourless long needles)	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ NS (235)	C 61.51 H 5.44	61.27 5.53
H	C ₃ H ₇	46	293-295 (Colourless needles)	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₂ NS (249)	C 63.07 H 5.70	62.65 6.02
H	n-C ₄ H ₉	53	306-308 (Colourless plates)	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ NS (263)	C 63.48 H 5.99	63.87 6.46
H	i-C ₄ H ₉	47	304-305 (Colourless long needles)	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ NS (263)	C 63.45 H 6.12	63.87 6.46
H	C ₂ H ₄ OH	50	292-294 (Colourless long needles)	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₃ NS (251)	C 57.65 H 4.78	57.37 5.17
H	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	45	270-272 (Colourless needles)	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ NS (285)	C 66.92 H 5.05	67.38 5.26
CH ₃	CH ₃	43	296-298 (Yellow tiny needles)	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ NS (235)	C 60.82 H 5.44	61.28 5.50
N(CH ₂) ₅		65	203-205 (Colourless tiny needles)	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₂ NS (275)	C 64.98 H 5.94	65.46 6.18
N(CH ₂) ₄ O		41	302-304 (Colourless needles)	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₃ NS (277)	C 60.30 H 4.98	60.64 5.44

All the above compounds were crystallised from chloroform.

Decomposition of 3-piperidinomethyl-4-hydroxy-1-thiacoumarin: A solution of 3-piperidinomethyl-4-hydroxy-1-thiacoumarin (1.37 g.) in water (50 ml.) containing acid-hydrochloric (1.5 ml.) was heated on steam bath for 24 hr. The yellow solid was filtered, washed with water. Crystallisation from chlorobenzene gave light yellow long needles, m.p. 303°. (Yield, 0.7 g.).

A mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of 3,3'-methylene bis-(4-hydroxy-1-thiacoumarin) did not show any depression. (C₁₉H₁₂O₄S₂ calculated: C, 61.95; H, 3.26; Found: C, 61.54; H, 2.99%).

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